

UNPOP REPORT ON METHODOLOGICAL OUTLINE (D2.1)

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Executive Summary

This report presents a consolidated account of the various methodological approaches employed across multiple studies examining populist parties, their emotion narratives, and broader political cultures in Portugal, Italy, and Spain. It integrates the protocols and techniques used in five research papers and one doctoral thesis, each of which focused on different yet complementary dimensions of populist mobilisation, emotion discourses, and political participation.

Overall, the collective investigations adopted both mixed and qualitative methodologies. Mixed-method designs included a combination of quantitative surveys and semi-structured interviews, permitting the triangulation of emotion narratives with objective measures such as populist attitude scales and vote intention. Qualitative methods drew on participant observation, discourse and narrative analyses, ethnography, focus groups, and free word association techniques, revealing how emotions, ideologies, and social representations interact in populist rhetoric and movement-party contexts. Ethical considerations were foregrounded throughout, following institutional review protocols and ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and data protection compliance. Analyses were supported by software such as SPSS (quantitative) and MAXQDA (qualitative), and by theoretical frameworks such as the Geneva Emotion Wheel for coding emotional expressions, as well as Greimas's actantial model and story grammar approaches for narrative structures.

Introduction

This report outlines the different methods used in the first set of UNPOP publications. It synthesises by methods adopted the main procedures followed for data collection and analysis. These publications investigate populist parties and their emotion narratives in Southern European contexts. The studies collectively examine a wide array of populist formations across the ideological spectrum, including radical right populist parties such as Chega (Portugal) and Fratelli d'Italia (Italy), left-wing populist parties such as Bloco de Esquerda (BE) and Partido Comunista Português (PCP) in Portugal, and so-called 'movement-parties' like the Movimento 5 Stelle (M5S) in Italy and Podemos in Spain. Despite differences in ideological positioning and political strategies, these parties share a reliance on emotional engagement in mobilising both supporters and broader electorates.

To capture these complexities, the papers utilised diverse research designs. First, they drew on standard qualitative techniques, including semi-structured interviews, ethnographic participant observation (offline and digital), and in-depth narrative analysis. Second, they implemented quantitative surveys focusing on emotion elicitation and populist attitudes, enabling the study of larger populations and comparisons across countries. Third, a set of specialised qualitative tools—discourse analysis, the free word association technique, and genealogical narrative methods—allowed for detailed exploration of how emotions, ideologies, and narratives intertwine.

Full information on the UNPOP publications are available on the UNPOP website at: <https://unpop.ces.uc.pt/en/publicacoes/>.

Methodology Outline

1. Surveys

Purpose and Rationale

Surveys enabled systematic measurement of emotional, cognitive, and attitudinal patterns in a wider population. They were especially useful for comparing levels of populist attitudes, emotional reactions to specific political issues, and voting intentions across different demographic groups.

Design and Content

- Sampling:
 - Some studies approximated quota sampling based on national census criteria (gender, age, education).
 - Large sample sizes (up to 1,900 respondents) to achieve robust statistical power.
- Survey Instruments include:
 - **Emotion batteries** (based on the [Geneva Emotion Wheel](#)) to capture specific emotional responses (e.g. fear, anger, joy, pride).
 - **Populist Attitude Scales** (12 items) measuring anti-elitism, chauvinism, anti-pluralism, and people-centrism, validated through factor analysis.
 - **Vote Intention** questions, employing a 0–10 scale, asking respondents about the likelihood of voting for each relevant party.
 - **Socio-demographic** details (e.g. age, gender, education level, region).

Data Analysis

- Employed descriptive statistics (e.g. frequency counts, means) and inferential tests (MANOVA, cluster analysis) using SPSS.
- Reliability testing (Cronbach's alpha) confirmed the coherence of populist attitudes sub-scales.
- Cluster analysis singled out distinct voter profiles (e.g. radical right-leaning vs. mainstream).

2. Semi-Structured Interviews

Purpose and Rationale

Interviews offered an in-depth look at how party representatives, Members of Parliament, and local activists construct emotional and ideological narratives

around populist politics. This method was particularly fruitful for uncovering personal motivations, party strategies, and nuanced emotion discourses.

Sample and Recruitment

- Ranged from small to moderate samples of individuals with insider knowledge of the parties (45 interviewees, comprising both MPs and grassroots members).
- Recruitment via direct contact or by press offices (in the case of elected officials) and publicly available details (for local activists).

Format and Procedure

- Interviews typically lasted 30–90 minutes.
- Guided by semi-structured protocols that allowed researchers to explore salient themes (e.g. anti-elitism, perception of corruption, stance on immigration) while leaving room for participants' spontaneous reflections.
- Audio-recorded (with consent) and fully transcribed.

Data Analysis

- Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke) or other qualitative frameworks (e.g. narrative analysis) implemented with software like MAXQDA.
- Coding categories ranged from broad political themes (anti-establishment, security, identity) to specific emotional references or rhetorical strategies.

4. Participant Observation / Ethnography

Purpose and Rationale

Ethnographic engagement—both offline and online—captures the lived experiences and emotional currents in political communities. This immersion reveals how party activists, sympathisers, or supporters enact populist discourses in everyday settings and digital platforms.

Offline Observation

- Researchers attended party meetings, assemblies, demonstrations, and informal gatherings.
- Daily fieldnotes documented interactions, recurring themes, and emotional atmospheres (e.g. enthusiasm, anger, disillusion).

Digital Ethnography

- Tracked party or movement activities on official platforms and social media (e.g. Facebook, Telegram, Reddit, Loomio).

- Collected data on how online discussions, polls, or debates reflect and shape “e-motions.”

Sampling

- Often emergent: researchers began by contacting local leaders or known activists, then expanded their networks through snowball sampling.
- Sought diversity by age, class, tenure in the party, and degree of leadership involvement.

Data Analysis

- Fieldnotes systematically coded to identify patterns in group dynamics, leadership styles, or conflict resolution.
- Triangulated with interview data to clarify how online/offline dimensions converge.

5. Focus Groups

Purpose and Rationale

Focus groups provided a collective forum for dialogue, capturing group-level dynamics, shared emotional narratives, and potential disagreements within party activists or voter segments.

Setup

- Each focus group included approximately 5–10 participants who were active in local party units or had relevant personal experiences.
- Moderators used a semi-structured guide with open-ended prompts about leadership, campaigning, ideology, and emotional triggers.

Data Collection

- Sessions typically lasted around two hours, with audio recording (and occasionally video, if appropriate).
- Observers noted non-verbal cues, group consensus/dissent, and emergent themes.

Analysis

- Transcripts underwent thematic analysis, focusing on collective narratives, shared frames, and internal divergences in emotional experiences.

6. Free Word Association

Purpose and Rationale

Free word association illuminated spontaneous, less filtered social representations, especially regarding minorities or other politically sensitive topics. This technique is associated with Abric's Structural Approach to Social Representations.

Procedure

- Participants were presented with stimulus words or expressions (e.g., "minorities," "immigration") and asked to list all terms that came to mind.
- The immediate, open nature of responses allowed for projective, uninhibited articulations.

Analysis

- Terms were categorised into central (frequently evoked, indicative of stable core beliefs) and peripheral (less frequent, context-dependent) elements.
- Results provided insights into how prejudices, stereotypes, or supportive attitudes are structured, revealing the emotional underpinnings of populist rhetoric concerning out-groups.

3. Discourse analysis on emotions

Purpose and Rationale

This approach focuses on how political texts (and related qualitative data) convey emotion narratives by identifying two levels of objects—

- A **deep-object**, representing something valuable but vulnerable in the political community; and
- A **shallow-object**, which can either threaten or safeguard the deep-object.

Operationalisation

- Researchers categorise references within political discourse—such as interviews, policy statements, or speeches—into deep-objects (e.g. "the people," "national sovereignty," "traditional values") and shallow-objects (e.g. "immigration," "elites," "the media"), examining whether these are framed as threats or as opportunities.

Analytical Process

1. **Identify Key Objects:** Researchers code transcripts to locate mentions of valuable/vulnerable items (deep-objects) and those cast as threats or opportunities (shallow-objects).
2. **Map Emotions:** Each object is labelled with the corresponding emotion reported or implied (e.g. anger directed at “elites,” pride in “the nation”).
3. **Interpret Frames:** The analysis uncovers how certain ideas or groups become ‘defended’ objects in the populist narrative, illuminating how leaders craft emotional attachments—or aversions—to shape political cultures and views on (un)democratic practices.

7. Narrative and Discourse Analysis

Purpose and Rationale

To capture the internal logic of populist storytelling—how party leaders and supporters construct worlds, conflicts, and solutions—narrative and discourse analysis is crucial.

Key Frameworks

1. Marie-Laure Ryan’s Four Dimensions:
 - **Spatial** (places, scales); **Temporal** (sequencing of events); **Mental** (agency, emotion, cognition); **Formal/Pragmatic** (causal chains, narrative coherence, and ‘tellability’).
2. Elliott’s (2005) Three Models:
 - **Content-Focused:** Identifying themes, myths, ideologies.
 - **Form-Focused:** Examining rhetorical/linguistic strategies.
 - **Pragmatic:** Considering the audience, goals, and context of narrative production.
3. Greimas’s Actantial Model
 - Mapping out roles such as Subject/Object, Adjuvant/Opponent, Sender/Receiver to highlight conflict and desire lines in populist discourse.

Data Sources

- Parliamentary speeches

Analysis Process

- **Identifying narrative arcs and structures** in leaders’ speeches (problem-solution sequences, emotional appeals).

- **Mapping Rhetorical Devices:** Assessing repeated discursive patterns, metaphor usage, and other discursive strategies to trigger collective identities
- **Evaluating Coherence:** Tracking how repeated events or metaphors create a sense of cohesion and credibility, fostering emotional resonance among audiences.

8. Lexicographic (Co-Occurrence) Analysis Using IRaMuTeQ

Purpose and Rationale

This method focused on analysing media-based data to uncover how journalists and political commentators shape emotional narratives around populist candidates. By leveraging a *lexicographic quantitative-qualitative* technique (via IRaMuTeQ software), researchers can detect co-occurrences of key terms and map how they cluster around specific emotions, ultimately illuminating how media discourse frames or reinforces populist themes.

Procedures

- **Transcription and Coding:** All content was transcribed verbatim; emotions were labelled according to Scherer's (2005) Geneva Emotion Wheel.
- **IRaMuTeQ Software:** The corpus was processed via **Similarity Analysis**, identifying co-occurrences among words and mapped emotions, revealing how journalists link candidates to specific emotional frames.

Analysis

- **Lexical Networks:** The software's output visualises clustered themes (e.g., "Ventura," "debate," "anger") and indicates how negative or positive emotions attach to each.
- **Interpretation:** Researchers examine the resulting networks to see which emotions appear dominant (e.g., anger vs. pride) and how they shape the media's portrayal of populist figures.